

BIRD IMPACT ON LEADING EDGE WING WITH SPH FORMULATION

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SUMMARY

With the need to reduce design life cycle time and costs with ever more complex aircraft structures the possibility of certification of aircraft structures against the birdstrike using advanced numerical tools is attractive. This paper presents a numerical investigation of the capability of a fiber metal sandwich wing leading edge construction subject to birdstrike by using finite element method coupled to smooth particle hydrodynamic method. Excellent qualitative correlation with experimental data were achieved.

Keywords: SPH, wing leading edge, fiber material laminate, bird strike, high speed

INTRODUCTION

Due to their attractive impact resistant properties Fiber Metal Laminates made with aluminum alloy and high strength glass fiber composite are a natural candidate material to be used for aircraft parts likely to be subjected to high velocity impacts originating for example from birds strike, runaway debris etc... To certify wing leading edge under birdstrike, aircraft manufacturer must ensure that the impact damage would still allow the aircraft to land safely .

Many researchers have investigated this phenomena using the different approaches for different aerospace structures. In [3] an SPH approach for modeling the bird impacting on the aircraft wing leading edge structures, was employed. In [7], the SPH method was developed to provide a transient structural analysis of fan blades during bird strikes while in [10] and [11], the bird impact numerical analyses was performed with finite element explicit codes, adopting the eulerian approach, and lagrangian approach respectively.

The leading edge is traditionally a secondary structure but it must be sized to meet high transient loads in case of impact. In a collaborative research project, aircraft wing leading edge structures with a glass-based FML skin have been designed, built, and subjected to bird strike tests that have been modeled with finite element analysis. In this work a coupled SPH/finite element model was developed for simulating the bird strike tests, where the Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) Lagrangian approach was used to model the bird and the FE method for the leading edge. Pre-test simulations correctly predicted that the bird did not penetrate the leading edge skin, and two different approaches were correlated to underline the behavior of the bird's model

correctly forecast that one FML lay-up would deform more than the other. Post test simulations included a model of the structure supporting the test article, and the predicted loads transferred to the supporting structure were in good agreement with the experimental values. The SPH bird model showed no signs of instability and correctly modeled the break-up of the bird into particles. The rivets connecting the skin to the ribs were found to have a profound effect on the performance of the structure.

The results related to the lagrangian approach on this structure were reported in a recent article [13]. This work deals with the detail of a finite element model using an explicit solver MSc/Dytran. This paper presents a numerical investigation of the capability of a fiber metal sandwich wing leading edge construction subject to birdstrike by using finite element method coupled to smooth particle hydrodynamic method. The SPH method, implemented in the explicit finite element code LS/Dyna, was used to model the bird in an impact on the leading edge configuration and with FML material. Detailed comparison with tests are made concerning the deformed shape of the bird and the structure.

Bird Modeling

In recent years, explicit computational codes have been used to develop high efficiency bird-proof structures. These codes adopted various numerical approaches to model the impact phenomena: the Lagrangian approach, Eulerian or Arbitrary Lagrangian Eulerian (ALE) approach, and recently solvers based on Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH).

Lagrangian Approach

The various formulations existent for the finite element analysis differ in the reference coordinates used to describe the motion and the governing equations. In the Lagrangian formulation, the nodes of the mesh are associated to particles in the material under examination; therefore, each node of the mesh follows an individual particle in motion. This formulation is used mostly to describe solid materials. The imposition of boundary conditions is simplified since the boundary nodes remain on the material boundary. Another advantage of the Lagrangian method is the ability to easily track history dependant materials. However, a Lagrangian description of this problem may result in loss of bird mass due to the fluid behavior of the bird which causes large distortions in the bird. In an explicit finite element analysis, the time step is determined by the smallest element dimension. The severe mesh distortion cause the time step to decrease to an unacceptably low value for the calculations to continue. These excessive distortions cause failure due to volumetric strain in some elements of the modeled bird.

SPH Approach

Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) formulation is a meshless Lagrangian technique used to model the fluid equations of motion using a pseudo-particle interpolation method to compute smooth hydrodynamic variables. During the 70's this method was used to simulate astrophysical phenomenon, but at the beginning of the 90's it has been used to resolve other physics problems in continuum mechanics, crash simulations, brittle and ductile fracture in solids. Due to the absence of a grid, this method allows researcher to solve many problems that are hardly reproducible in other classical methods such as mesh distortions and large displacements. Another advantage of the SPH method is that due to the absence of a mesh, problems with irregular geometry can

be solved. In this formulation, the fluid is represented as a set of moving particles, each one representing an interpolation point, where all the fluid properties are known. These particles have a spatial distance (known as the "smoothing length", typically represented in equations by h), over which their properties are "smoothed" by a kernel function. The contributions of each particle to a property are weighted according to their distance from the particle of interest, and their density. Mathematically, this is governed by the kernel function (symbol W). Kernel functions commonly used include the Gaussian function and the cubic spline. The latter function is exactly zero for particles further away than two smoothing lengths (unlike the Gaussian, where there is a small contribution at any finite distance away). This has the advantage of saving computational effort by not including the relatively minor contributions from distant particles. The equation for any quantity A at any point r is given by the equation

$$A(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_j m_j \frac{A_j}{\rho_j} W(|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_j|, h), \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

where m_j is the mass of particle j , A_j is the value of the quantity A for particle j , ρ_j is the density associated with particle j , r denotes position and W is the kernel function mentioned above. For example, the density of particle i (ρ_i) can be expressed as:

$$\rho_i = \rho(\mathbf{r}_i) = \sum_j m_j \frac{\rho_j}{\rho_j} W(|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j|, h) = \sum_j m_j W(\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j, h), \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

where the summation over j includes all particles in the simulation. Furthermore a real fluid can be modeled as many fluid particles provided that the particles are small compared to the scale over which macroscopic properties of the fluid varies, but large enough to contain many molecules so macroscopic properties can be defined sensibly. A large number of particles are needed for the SPH calculations, since the continuum limit is recovered when the number of particles goes to infinity. Particles in the SPH method carry information about their hydrodynamic and thermodynamic information, this in addition to the mass needed to specify the evolution of the fluid. Nodes in SPH are similar to nodes in a mesh, the difference is that these nodes are continuously deformable and distort automatically to put more of the computational effort in regions of relatively high density. One disadvantage in SPH is that this method is computationally demanding, both in memory and in CPU time. This can be overcome using a parallel analysis with more than one CPU. There is also the difficulty of establishing the boundary condition when using the SPH method. Another disadvantage is that particles may penetrate the boundaries and causing loss of smoothness and accuracy.

Material Constitutive Models

In this section are reported the materials, that was used to experimental tests. Preliminary validation of the bird-strike test methodology was achieved through a series of tests and simulations on a simplified but representative structure, developed and manufactured specifically for this purpose by Alenia. Those tests have been useful to identify the best configuration capable to optimize the weight and performance and have given the opportunity to correlate the results with numerical results, which have been extended to the experimental full scale test on the tailcone. The bay of the leading edge

of the representative structure is shown in figure 1. Typical dimensions of the bay is 640 mm x 330 mm and thickness of the rib is 2 mm. A number of different impact scenarios were considered in order to identify the worst case scenario and to get insight into the impact behavior of the component by changing various parameters such as thickness ,materials, and the layup of configuration. The optimum weight/performance ratio consists of an outboard ply in FML, the core in honeycomb and an inboard ply in aluminum alloy 2024T3.

figure 1 – Leading edge’s bay

The inboard ply of the layup was a sheet of aluminum alloy 2024 T3 with a thickness of 0.3mm. The material law used for the aluminum alloy was an isotropic elastic plastic model, where it has defined a bilinear yield model with isotropic hardening, using the von Mises yield criterion with a plasticity algorithm that includes the strain rate effects. The strain rate dependency was included in the material law for the aluminum alloy layers. Cowper-Symonds law was used as the elastic-plastic formulation to consider strain rate sensitivity at medium rate regime, where the parameters D and p typically of the Cowper Symonds were equal to $D=1.28E+5s^{-1}$ and $p=4.0$, [14]. The material properties are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 - Aluminum alloy material properties

Young Modulus	Yield Stress	Ultimate Strength	Failure Strain
[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	%
72	280	385	18

The failure strain was 18% [15] and an isotropic damage law was implemented within the code based on a maximum equivalent plastic strain. The material fails completely when the plastic strain reaches beyond the defined limit. The element no longer carries any load and is removed from the calculation.

The FML used for the outboard ply was an hybrid material made of that consists of an aluminum ply alternated with a fiber glass, with a total thickness of 1.4mm. For the FML fiber metal laminate shell elements an the "orthotropic material model" was used. The material describes the elastic behavior of brittle material with failure based on the

interactive stress criteria of failure per mode. It includes the effects of directionality in the material stress-strain response allowing a different fiber orientation to be specified at each through thickness integration point for shell elements. Unidirectional laminated fiber composite shell thickness, each unidirectional layer (lamina) fiber orientation, and unidirectional layer constitutive constants are required as input by the user. The glass fibre/epoxy layers were modeled with homogenized linear elastic orthotropic materials, and the elasto-plastic characteristic of aluminum layers were modeled with bilinear isotropic hardening materials behavior using the von Mises yield criterion. In general, phenomenological strength criteria such as maximum stress and Chang-Chang criteria are used to detect the failure status of composite laminates. Due to the complexity of failure mechanisms in the FML material, it is difficult to define an applicable failure criterion. However, it is expected that the uniaxial static tensile failure of FML material is dominated by properties of glass fibre/epoxy composite layers, and the laminate fails just after the fibre breakage. So, the maximum strain failure criterion was used to predict the failure load in this study, and fracture is expected to occur when the strain in glass/epoxy layers reach the ultimate failure strain because aluminum has a much higher ductility than the fibre/epoxy composite layer. The basis of the model is the modification made in [16], to the well known Chang and Chang composite damage model. For the honeycomb core material behavior, an "Orthotropic Crushable Material Model" was used, during crushing the elastic modulus varies from their initial values to the fully compacted values. After the initial elastic region, the yielding behavior starts when the maximum stress in each face reaches the flow stress of the material making up the cell walls, which is given by:

$$\sigma = \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{t}{l} \right)^2 \cdot \sigma_y \quad \text{eq. 3}$$

Considering that the thickness of an individual sheet t was equal to 0.145 mm, l , the length of each of the cell faces, was equal to 6.35 mm, and $\sigma_Y = 100\text{MPa}$, the yielding behavior started when the stress is 34.7kPa. When the compressed volume of the cell became 20% of the initial volume the honeycomb behave like an aluminum layer, which is defined the maximum failure strain of 18%.

Finite element modeling

Two different codes were used to compare the classical FE approach to the coupled FE/SPH (MSC/Dytran (19) and LS/DYNA) to predict the effects of bird-strike on the leading edge. In this section the classical FE results are correlated to the experimental results. The model (figure 2) contains the bird, one leading edge skin, two ribs, the load frame, and the leading edge was also modeled in details i.e. skin and core. For this test the planned impact angle was 90° with an impact speed equal to 129 m/s and the bird mass was 3.68kg. The outboard skin contained 4.544 shell elements with a relatively uniform mesh, the sandwich honeycomb core was modeled with eight-node brick, this ply contained 12.240 elements. The two ribs contained 1422 shell elements, ((-b), and the horizontal beams were linked to the outboard skin and interface beam with the fittings, discretized using four nodes shell elements ((-a). The bird element were modeled with eight-node brick, this one contained 2938 elements. it was shaped as a cylinder of 268mm long and a diameter of recreated 134mm diameter ((-c). The total

number of specimen's finite elements were 37.407. In case of SPH modeling, a bird with different shape was used.

figure 2 – Leading edge FE model

SPH Modelling

The SPH method [2], implemented in the explicit finite element code LS/Dyna, was used to model the birdstrike. In keeping with the current standard practice for bird-strike modeling, the bird model geometry was approximately here as a right circular cylinder with hemispherical end caps as shown in figure 3.

figure 3 – Geometry of bird model

The density of the bird was 950kg/m^3 obtaining an average value equal to about 95% that of water, as suggested by [4]. The water-like behaviour of the bird was simulated in LS/Dyna with an elastic-plastic hydrodynamics model, [17], where the pressure-volume relationship is governed by an equation of state (EOS) and it behaves as an elastic-plastic material at low pressure. The identification of the parameters for the bird model is done using results obtained in the studies reported in [3].

Results comparison

In this section the SPH results are compared to the classical FE approach. In the two numerical model used are shown. It is worth mentioning that for the classical FE the bird was modeled using a cylinder shape while for the SPH approach the bird was modeled with the hemispherical end caps. The choice to use a cylindrical bird was forced by the need to obtaining a stable analysis, because the large deformations of the hemispherical shape caused premature failure of the analysis. This is not applicable to SPH approach and it was preferred to consider a cylinder shape. In figure 5 to figure 8, the evolution of the impact is reported, and the deformation behavior of the structure

according to the classical FE bird model appears to be in excellent agreement with the SPH model. The differences are evident on the deformation behavior of the bird, infact the FE bird, figure 5, as soon as it impacts the structure starts it is evident that FE mesh undergoes large distortions and, this cause a decreasing of the time step to not unacceptable low value for the calculations to continue since in an explicit finite element analysis, the time step is determined by the smallest element dimension.

figure 4 – Bird model, Lagrangian and SPH

figure 5 – Impact for the Lagrangian modeling at 2 and 3.6ms

figure 6 – Two steps of the impact for the SPH modeling at 2 and 3.6ms

figure 7 – Top view of the Lagrangian modeling at 2 and 3.6ms

figure 8 – Top view of the SPH modeling at 2 and 3.6ms

figure 9 – Numerical and experimental shape after the impact

On the contrary, the SPH model (see figure 6) the bird flows around the structure and break up into a debris particles and this approach reproduces the bird-strike behavior, visually, in a way closer to common experience. Both simulations show that the leading edge configuration is able to withstand the specified impacts without the birds

penetrating the nose skin. For both simulation approaches the failure mechanism of the structure is close to the one observed in the experimental test. It is evident that the results of the simulations demonstrate that the SPH and classical FE model are particularly reliable to reproduce in details the dynamic of the event during the normal evolution of the impact. In general, the simulation results for the classical FE SPH techniques are shown to be in good agreement however, and the SPH bird produced a different way to deform. Similar to the classical FE model results [13], as shown in Figure 5, the shape of the deformation using the SPH approach is very similar. In figure 10, the maximum deformation on the leading edge analyzed by SPH approach is shown. The maximum deformation was 297 mm, which is lower than the real value recorded during the experimental test (390mm), while for the classical FE bird lagrangian approach the value was 410 mm. This difference about the deformation is a convincing argument that the SPH may still be immature to reproduce experimental data, however, the SPH approach produced a more realistic global deformation than the classical FE approach.

figure 10 – Maximum deformation of the SPH modeling at 3.6ms

Conclusions

This paper presented the work performed to design a wing leading edge by employing the finite element method coupled to a meshless method in order to reduce the experimental costs. In particular, a classical FE approach was adopted to model the wing leading edge while Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) was used for modelling the bird. Excellent qualitative correlation between the SPH bird numerical model and the experimental test were obtained in terms of global deformations mode while for the quantitative comparison difference were found when measuring the highest deformation.

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